

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

TOURISM OPEN-ENDED EXPERIMENTATION PLATFORM

Co-designed strategy to improve product/experience portfolio, to promote the concept of a sustainable and integrated tourism supply chain and to innovate territorial touristic communication and narration.

SPOKE N 3 – Tourism and culture industry

FP TOEP - TOURISM OPEN-ENDED EXPERIMENTATION PLATFORM

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Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.

Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

1. Introduction

1.1 Scenario

The tourism offer in Piedmont is very active and dynamic: every day throughout the region, there are both permanent initiatives (such as exhibitions and museums) and temporary ones (such as food festivals, events lasting only a weekend or a few days). The problem with this vast array of initiatives is their poor dissemination both in traditional media (television, radio, and newspapers) and in more modern ones (especially social media). Therefore, a tourist who wants to know what is happening in a specific area of Piedmont has to check all the aforementioned media to understand what the tourist offers are. This effort, in addition to being very time-consuming, is ineffective.

In the first part of this project, we contacted many tourist offices in various areas of Piedmont (Alessandria, Gavi, Alba, Turin, just to name a few) in order to understand how to solve the aforementioned problem. We found that each tourism board had a very personal way of managing the promotion of events and therefore it was difficult to integrate it with other initiatives of other tourism boards. We then had some meetings with VisitPiedmont in order to define a common data structure for all events so that all the initiatives of all the boards can be presented in the same way and therefore that a user, having access to an app capable of visualizing these initiatives in a user-friendly way, can have a complete overview of them and can therefore choose their experiences more accurately.

2. Development

2.1 Aim

TOEP is a mobile and web application designed to consolidate various regional activities within Piedmont into a centralized platform. The application leverages a recommendation system and a user-friendly interface to present users with activities aligned with their preferences. Moreover, it enables tour operators to promote their offerings (e.g., gastronomic events, hikes, museums) and track user engagement.

2.2 Users

TOEP caters to two primary user segments:

- **Users:** This group employs the platform to discover activities that align with their individual profiles, factoring in interests, current location, and recommendations from other users. Users may include tourists, travelers, residents, and more.

- Providers: These entities utilize the platform to disseminate, advertise, and assess their tourism initiatives. Providers can encompass enterprises, associations, public agencies, accommodation facilities, and private operators.

2.3 Architecture

Figure 1. TOEP High Level Architecture

TOEP comprises a web interface for providers and a mobile app for users, both integrated with a flexible cloud-based MongoDB database for scalability. The mobile and web apps are being developed using modern technologies such as Ionic Framework, Node.js, Firebase, and TypeScript, to handle user requests, user interface design, and communication with the database. The Recommendation System is being implemented using machine learning algorithms to analyse user data and generate personalized recommendations.

2.4 Provider (web interface)

Providers have a web-based portal that allows them to:

- Activity management: Create, edit, delete, and publish new tourism activities (Fig. 1, letter a).
- Customization: Configure details such as schedules, prices, detailed descriptions, and attach images or videos.
- Performance data: Access information on the performance of their activities, including bookings, reviews, and user ratings (Fig. 1, letter d).

The platform's data collection process is designed to be flexible and adaptable to the diverse range of activities offered by providers. The specific information required for each activity is determined by its assigned category and type:

- Categories: art, towns, food, religion, nature, wellness, shows, special, fairs, exhibitions, traditions, music, sport, outdoor, and entertainment.
- Types: activity, event or itinerary.

2.5 Users

Users can:

- Profile Creation: Complete a detailed profile to improve the accuracy of recommendations and save their activity category preferences and their favorite activities (Fig. 1, letter b).
- Online Bookings: Make reservations directly from the app and receive instant confirmations.
- Ratings: Rate and leave comments on completed activities, contributing to the improvement of the information available on the platform (Fig. 1, letter e).
- Personalized Search: Conduct a Map-based activity search based on their interests, location, and other criteria
- Intelligent Recommendations: Receive personalized activity suggestions thanks to a recommendation system that analyzes their preferences and the behavior of similar users (Fig. 1, letter c).

Figure 2. Profile page

Figure 3. Web App - Home page for Users

To enhance user experience, the mobile application categorizes suggestions into three main groups as illustrated in Figure 2. This categorization scheme empowers users to quickly identify activities that align with their specific interests and needs.

- **Inspired activities** are closely aligned with a user's individual preferences, providing highly personalized recommendations.
- **Near You** suggestions prioritize activities located in proximity to the user's current location.
- **Highlighted activities** represent the platform's top-rated and most popular options.

The user profile (Fig. 3) page allows users to adjust their preferences at any time. Here, users can modify their preferences, view a list of favorited activities, and access a history of their past participations, complete with review options.

3. Conclusion

The application is currently in a production-ready state, providing a robust feature set for both providers and users. Users can explore detailed activity information, add activities to their favourites, enrol in activities, and provide feedback. Providers can manage their activity listings, including creation, modification, and deletion. Additionally, they can oversee enrolments and track attendance. About the recommendation system, it is currently in development.